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FEMaLe

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

1. All WP impact monitoring & assessment reports

This report will contain impact monitoring and assessment (IMA) in all WPs in the FEMaLe projects.

The IMA report contains 3 sections: 1) FEMaLe Pulse Checks, 2) Impact Case workshop results and 3) Half Double evaluation. This will be the structure of reporting in all future “All WP IMA reports”.

The purpose of FEMaLe Pulse Checks is to navigate the project with stakeholder satisfaction, it can create insights and dialogue needed amongst key stakeholders to ensure continuous focus on impact, energizing working conditions, collaboration, and personal development on the project. The Pulse check will be conducted in an online survey in SurveyXact. FEMaLe pulse check will be using the pulse check questions from half double methodology.

The purpose of Impact Case workshop results report is to establish an overview of how to go from project's deliverables to create project value. The description includes a hierarchy of goals for desired impacts and behavioral impacts we need to see to realize the overall impacts. The Impact Case workshop results will contain all WP Impact Cases and action points noted from the workshops, it will give an overview for the FEMaLe partners, monitor their impact creation progress, and help the partners to realize impact faster.

The purpose of Half Double evaluation is to get insight into how each work package works with the Half Double Methodology to improve and validate project activities. The evaluation has been conducted as a constructive evaluation based on qualitative interviews with the work package leader(s) and the project coordinator. Each work package is then scored on the extent to which they use the Half Double methodology, and then given reflective questions to improve their individual work. The aim is to increase impact and to capture the full potential in the project.

2. FEMaLe Pulse Checks

16 out of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries have signed and returned the WP1 informed consent form (100%).

16 out of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries responded to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire (100%).

FEMALE BENEFICIARY	RESPONSE (NUMBER)	ICF	MAIN WPs
AARHUS UNIVERSITET	Y (2)	Y	3,8,10
AARHUS UNIVERSITETSHOSPITAL	Y (1)	Y	6,7
EUROPEAN SOCIETY FOR QUALITY AND PATIENT SAFETY IN GENERAL PRACTICE/FAMILY MEDICINE	Y (1)	Y	1,9
SEMMELWEIS EGYETEM	Y (3)	Y	5,6,7
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	Y (1)	Y	4,9
SURGAR	Y (1)	Y	6,7
RIGAS TEHNISKA UNIVERSITATE	Y (1)	Y	4,6,7
KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN	Y (1)	Y	5
ISTANBUL AVRUPA ARASTIRMALARI DERNEGI	Y (1)	Y	2
PRECISIONLIFE LTD	Y (1)	Y	4
YOURCODE LAB INFORMATIKAI, SZOLGALTATO ES TANACSADO KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	Y (1)	Y	5,8
THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN	Y (2)	Y	3
CORRELATE AS	Y (1)	Y	10
NEMANJA TODIC PREDUZETNIK WEB BAY	Y (1)	Y	9
EGYUTT KONNYEBB NOI EGESZSEGERT ALAPITVANY	Y (1)	Y	2,9
THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	Y (2)	Y	3

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: September 2021

A total of 17 FEMaLers replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 15 of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusions:

85% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,3 of 5 (+0,3).

76% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,2).

94% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,3 of 5 (-).

64% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 3,9 of 5 (+0,1).

76% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: October 2021

A total of 19 FEMaLers replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 15 of 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusions:

85% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,4).

79% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,3).

95% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,1).

69% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

79% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: November 2021

A total of 20 FEMaLers replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing all 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusions:

85% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,4).

80% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,3).

95% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,1).

70% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

80% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,4).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: December 2021

A total of 21 FEMaLers replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing all 16 FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusions:

86% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,4).

81% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,3).

95% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,1).

71% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

81% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,4).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

Average score	September	October	November	December
Question 1	4.3 (+0.3)	4.4 (+0.4)	4.4 (+0.4)	4.4 (+0.4)
Question 2	4.1 (+0.2)	4.2 (+0.3)	4.2 (+0.3)	4.2 (+0.3)
Question 3	4.3 (-)	4.4 (+0.1)	4.4 (+0.1)	4.4 (+0.1)
Question 4	3.9 (+0.1)	4.1 (+0.3)	4.1 (+0.3)	4.1 (+0.3)
Question 5	4.1 (+0.3)	4.1 (+0.3)	4.2 (+0.4)	4.2 (+0.4)

Table 1: The table illustrates the pulse check question scores over specific months. It allows comparisons between the scores over the specific months.

Pulse Check Summary

Overall, the FEMaLe PMO is extremely proud and happy to learn how every FEMaLe Consortium member finds it stimulating, rewarding, and meaningful to be working in the project, enabling effective and efficient processes. As such, we are on the right track in realizing a frictionless stream of results and impact (flow), based on collaborative project leadership.

Also, it appears that the FEMaLe Consortium is quite satisfied with how the FEMaLe Project Manager and Coordinator is leading the complex system of human beings, embracing the inevitable uncertainty, and making the project happen, especially facilitating a people process with high energy in interactions and solving complex project problems in the process.

Action Points

We will continue to have fun and act in an appreciative way to bring energy into every FEMaLe encounter.

We will show and communicate clearly about how each FEMaLer contributes to create early impact.

We will focus on improving relations, collaborations, and deliverables by utilizing Correlate FEMaLe and online tools (as described in deliverables 9.2 FEMaLe Dissemination Package and 10.22 Data-driven digital management platform).

We will plan and conduct interviews with FEMaLers about how the FEMaLe PMO may support their personal and professional developments working in FEMaLe (as part of additional interview to establish the Half Double Constructive Evaluation Baseline – see Section 4 below).

These are the four top priorities before the next *All WP IMA reports* due M18.

3. Results of the Impact Case workshops

The Impact Case workshop results report will contain all WP Impact Cases, action points noted from the workshops and risk assessment, it will give an overview for the FEMaLe partners, monitor their impact creation progress, and help the partners to realize impact faster. The results of the Impact Case workshops are based on workshops with the work package leader(s), WP1 leader and the project coordinator.

In 2021 autumn/winter, the actions of the FEMaLe WP1 are described below:

- July, August, and September were used to plan and coordinate Impact Case workshops.
- October and November were used to facilitate the Impact Case workshops.
- December was used to complete Deliverable 1.4.

The action plan of 2022 winter/spring for FEMaLe WP1 is described below:

- Establish impact solution design workshops in January and February
- Tracking and mitigation during the WP leader meeting to report their progression of their work package.
- Navigate the project stakeholder satisfaction by sending out FEMaLe Pulse Check report in May
- Complete deliverable 1.5 in June

The following section will contain all Impact Case workshops, impact map, KPIs, action points, severity of the risk of not completing the action/task, the description of the action points and actions to minimize the risks. If the action point is completed; the risk will not be evaluated.

WP1

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To create 11 Half Double and Impact Case workshops
2. To create 10 Impact cases

Were the targets met?

Yes, we reached the intended targets. We conducted 11 Half Double and Impact Case workshops and created 10 Impact Cases.

We facilitated an Impact Case workshop with all WP to strengthen and accelerate capacity to reduce time to benefit and impact.

We created a workflow description, to establish a specific work frequency in the WP1 team.

We sent out pulse checks in a specific frequency.

We created an action plan for WP1 IMA for 2022.

WP2

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To identify 10 advisers and professionals in ethics, gender inclusion, RRI and open science.
2. To invite 10 advisers and professionals in ethics, gender inclusion, RRI and open science.
3. To identify 10 good practices and advisers for gender inclusion, RRI and open science.
4. To create an action plan for responsible innovation and research (including gender equity, inclusion, open sciences etc.)

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP2 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2. This has no critical consequences, as the next deliverables are due much later in the FEMaLe project.

We intended to conduct meetings/workshops with all FEMaLe WPs to discuss how to integrate responsible research and innovation (RRI) in their work packages, respectively. However, we soon realised that the FEMaLe partners need additional guidance on RRI and inclusion in their corresponding WP. The WP2 Leader will invite and coordinate WP Leader meetings in early 2022 to identify unmet needs.

To establish significant RRI and inclusion standard baseline in FEMaLe, WP2 needs to explore the best practices and advisers for gender inclusion, RRI and open sciences. Without this, FEMaLe project will not reach the significant standard of gender inclusion, RRI and open sciences.

We wanted to identify best practices and advisers on ethics (subject matter experts on gender, inclusion, open science, and innovation.), we established contact with few advisers, and the task will continue in Q1 2022. This task will be ongoing throughout the project to continuously improve the RRI, inclusion and open sciences aspect of the FEMaLe project.

We wanted to create an action plan for responsible innovation and research (including gender equity, inclusion, RRI, Open Sciences etc.) in the FEMaLe project. The public expects us to act responsibly, and responsible innovation creates spaces and processes to explore innovation and its consequences in an open, inclusive, and timely way. Without the action plan FEMaLe will not be able to create an effective plan of how to maintain IRR in FEMaLe. The actions plan is still ongoing, and it will be finished in Q1 2022.

We will create a monitoring plan for gender, inclusion, RRI, open sciences etc. After the completion of the action plan mentioned above, gender inclusion, RRI and open sciences will be monitored and continuously maintained in FEMaLe.

WP3

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To obtain ethical and data approvals.
2. To employ 4 dedicated staffs.
3. To disseminate online and offline in the UK.
4. To produce an action plan for launching the large-scale questionnaire.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP3 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

In Denmark the application for data approval is close to submission. The plan is to submit before 1st February. In the UK, the ethical approval has been sought and the ethics board has confirmed that formal ethics application is not needed. Data approvals application is completed in UK, WP3 aim to submit the data approvals application within February.

WP3 intended to employ 4 dedicated staffs. In Denmark, a PhD student has started and a call for a post doc has been prepared. In the UK, WP3 have appointed a statistician PhD fellow and another experienced statistician to help with big data analysis and development of a prediction model.

It is intended to disseminate online and offline in the UK. FEMaLe project has been widely advertised. It was featured in British Society of Gynaecology Endoscopy quarterly SCOPE magazine in March 2021, which is disseminated to all BSGE members (including doctors, nurses, and trainees in the UK with interest in laparoscopy and endometriosis).

Dr Saraswat talked about the FEMaLe project in a presentation 'Endometriosis in the UK: Time for change' in the Australian Gynaecology Endoscopy Society annual meeting in Oct 2021. Profs Horne and Saunders and Dr Saraswat regularly tweet and retweet messages from FEMaLe to increase awareness about the project. Further, Ayansina, Dolapo presented the protocol at the Endometriosis network meeting. The dissemination task on social media is ongoing.

Furthermore, it is WP3 needed to produce an action plan for launching the large-scale questionnaire, but it has some difficulties to make, because of the uncertainties of we do not know how long it will take the Danish health authorities to approve the data application. This task will be postponed for the next WP3 Impact Case. The action plan will be completed in 2022.

WP4

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To get Aalborg University approved as FEMaLe beneficiary to establish rhythm and flow in WP4.
2. To employ 3 dedicated staffs.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP4 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

Aalborg has not yet been accepted as a partner; we still await answers from Aarhus University. This is a serious problem, but we have contacted the administration, the situation is out of our hands, and we can only await an answer. This has consequences of delaying starting the WP4 tasks.

Furthermore, the WP4 intended to recruit 3 dedicated staff from AU, AAU, and Oxford. This task is reached. The recruitment is following; Kristina Maggaard Koldby in AAU, Nilufer in Oxford, and Maria Pencheri in AU.

WP5

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To generate a recruitment plan per target country to attract Lucy App users.
2. To validate and translate the content of the Lucy App into Danish and Swedish.
3. To validate the baseline questionnaire.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP5 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

Regarding to generate a recruitment plan per target country to attract Lucy App users. WP5 decided to use the help of the self-help groups and national endometriosis organizations in every country. These organizations will have the task of the recruitment for the Lucy App users to fill the questionnaire. Every country who will be attending this study part, should organize their own recruitment. We will need only the contacts to follow-up the recruitment process and involvement in the study. This will be followed up upon next workshop.

The Lucy App is validated and translated in Danish and Swedish. Furthermore, to validate the baseline questionnaire. We have the questionnaire in Hungarian and in English, only the research call needs to be translated into English, so other parties can do the translation to their own language and start the study country-by-country. Moreover, to establish flow by setting up the FEMaLe discord channel for instant communication. All WP5 members are connected in the discord channel.

WP6 & WP7

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To define tasks needed to subcontract, clarify budget, and get administration approval.
2. To recruit 10 annotators.
3. To reach 1 new scientific collaborator.
4. To reach legal and ethical approvals.
5. To reach 2 subcontracts
6. To establish an event with French policy makers to promote FemTech and Endometriosis.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP6-WP7 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

Regarding to define tasks needed to subcontract, clarify budget, and get administration approval. WP6-WP7 agreed on transferring Aarhus tasks budget to SurgAR for collection and annotation. The task is already in progression, this will be followed up upon next workshop.

6 annotators are ready and 4 are passing the entry exam. They will be ready in early 2022.

WP6-WP7 have established contract with 3 healthcare centers as potential video collection partners.

It is ongoing to reach legal and ethical approvals for the 3 healthcare centers.

The French president recently presented its action plan for endometriosis management. Pr. Bourdel participated to its design and establishment with the French Health Ministry.

WP8

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To test the pilot program modules.
2. To translate the video into English and Hungarian.
3. To validate and translate the My Endo program.
4. To generate a recruitment plan for the My Endo program.
5. To establish contact with Endometriosis Units/Clinics and Patient Associations.
6. To investigate the capacity of the recruitment of the RCT and how to increase it

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP8 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2. WP8 agreed to start the pilot program modules in February 2022.

Regarding to translate the video into English and Hungarian, the transcription of all videos is still in progress. The validation and translation of My Endo program is still ongoing and will be done later in 2022.

Furthermore, the tasks: to generate a recruitment plan for the My Endo program, to establish contact with Endometriosis Units/Clinics and Patient Associations and to investigate the capacity of the recruitment of the RCT and how to increase it. They will not be done until validation is finished or another post.doc is hired. This will be taken into consideration and followed up in the WP8 Impact Case Q1+Q2 2022.

WP9

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To develop the FEMaLe's website and a communication plan.
2. To establish workshops to identify 2 relevant events.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP9 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

Web-bay is working on the website. The main part is developed (It can be viewed here: <https://female-dev.webbaysolutions.com/>), but the internal pages are yet to be done. WP9 had a hold up with the content for internal pages, but it is solved. So, the task will be continued in early 2022.

Additionally, WP9 need more information from the partners, such as: their logos, signed consent form that we can use their logo on the website, short bios of each partner and their consent to publish it all of which is still in progress. This task will be followed up on next workshop.

Communication plan is complete, and it was developed by Web-bay and EQuIP. In 2022 there will be FEMaLe partner promotion. 1st of February 2022, FEMaLe will host a webinar. Throughout March 2022, we will run 'Endometriosis Awareness Month' campaign based on a collaboration with the Danish patient association. In addition, we may also have a panel debate, to debate issues with endometriosis, gender equality and so on. The panel debate will include scientists from various relevant disciplines and patients.

Regarding to establish workshops to identify two relevant events. For 2022, EQuIP and AU have identified events: Young People and Endometriosis. Social Perspectives on the Delay to Diagnosis in February, and EEL webinar in June. However, WP9 did not successfully establish workshops to reach collective consensus. This will be followed up on in the next workshop.

WP10

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the tasks?

1. To demonstrate the Correlate prototype platform to the FEMaLe consortium.
2. To conduct a needs assessment about usage of Correlate in the FEMaLe Project.
3. To create Correlate training sessions/workshops for the FEMaLe partners.
4. To establish a Correlate support team for the FEMaLe partners.
5. To pulse check FEMaLe stakeholders to monitor level of satisfaction.
6. To establish 5 Correlate seminar.
7. To identify Correlate folder structure.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP10 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

The Correlate platform has been introduced to WP leaders, showing the core features of the platform and how it works. The next step in this process is to onboard the WP leaders to Correlate by having a walkthrough session, showing participants how to use the platform, and letting them do it on their own. Part of this step will also include letting the WP leaders to invite the members of the team to each work package.

In the needs assessment step two initiatives have been conducted. First of all, members of the FEMaLe project have been sent a survey with questions related to the use of integrations and general feedback related to features members would like to see in Correlate. Secondly, a needs assessment workshop was conducted in November in Aarhus with different activities related to understanding which features should be developed to better support the project. The activities conducted in the needs assessment activities have been summarized and used as a foundation for developing the roadmap for development of new features in Correlate. The roadmap will be reassessed based on feedback from the project over time.

The first real training session will be conducted with the WP leaders. To involve other partners and provide support, follow up training sessions with all partners continuously throughout the project are also planned to take place once the partners have been invited to the platform. As part of this initiative, we are also working on a product walkthrough, to guide users through their first use of Correlate and get an understanding of key features.

This point has changed a bit based on discussions with members in the FEMaLe project. Instead of having a team dedicated to support, the plan is instead to have a board specifically related to support for the structure of the FEMaLe project and way of working. To support users with how to use the platform on a general level we plan to create a knowledge base with articles where users can find all the support information that they need and will be continuously updated based on the feedback from the project.

This initiative will start once members of the FEMaLe project have started using Correlate. After users have become introduced to the platform surveys will be sent out continuously to pulse check the level of satisfaction and get feedback about specific features.

Five Correlate seminars will be conducted either in person or digitally. To this date, the first seminar was conducted as the needs assessment workshop held in Aarhus during November 2021. A second seminar is also planned. Follow up seminars will be held continuously to get feedback about upcoming prototypes.

The initial folder structure has been set, to have one team with general information for all partners (FEMaLe Hub) and one team with continuous updates about the project and following up on tasks (Project Reporting), as well as set up individual teams for the different work packages to structure and set up the work for the specific WP. Initial templates have been created for the FEMaLe Hub and for the WPs. Templates for the Project Reporting team will be set up in the following period.

3. Half Double Constructive Evaluation

The following section contains the results of a constructive evaluation of the individual work packages of the FEMaLe project. The evaluation is based on individual baseline interviews with the work package leader(s) and the project coordinator. The evaluation is the first of a series of evaluations throughout the project. The evaluation is done in collaboration with the Half Double research team.

The aim of the evaluation is to get an insight into how each work package works with the Half Double Methodology (HDM) in order to improve and validate project activities.

The Half Double Methodology is built upon what research and experience tells us is needed to capture the full potential in our projects.

By implementing this methodology, each work package hopefully will increase greater impact and speed in the WP while reducing time. Furthermore, is a reflective mindset a guideline for how to think constructively about the work package and the work packages context.

The evaluation consists of four parts: project outcome, project characteristics and project processes as well as questions for reflections from the research team based on the former three parts.

1. Project outcome

The outcome perspective aims at generating an understanding of the projects impact, as discribed in 3. the Impact Case. This part is omitted in the following section.

2. Project characteristics

The projects charateristics is based on information about both project type, size and scale. Furthermore, is the project mapped according to its 1) pace, 2) novelty, 3) tecnology and 4) complexity, which is divided into a) project environment, b) project tasks and processes and c) project resources and organization which is rated on a scale from 1 (low) to 4 (high).

All ratings are accumulated into one score - labbeled Project scale, which ranges from 0 (low) to 17 (high). The work packaged characteristics is illustrated in a spiderweb chart (radar chart) for each work packaged, and will be further explained in the following sections for each work package.

3. Project processes

The project is mapped according to the practices of the Half Double Methodology. The mapping is based on a rating of the behavior of the Work Package leader on a scale from 1 to 4, where 1 is low application and 4 is high application of the practice (0 is practice not applicable). An average score works as a threshold for whether the work package is considered to have implemented the HDM (>2.5 : uses the HDM, <2.5 : does not use the HDM).

4. Questions for reflections

Based on the previous three parts, each work package is given some questions for reflection, this as part of the constructive evaluation in order to get the work packages to constructively reflect on their work process.

The learning perspective aims at generating constructive lessons learned. The questions are intended as discussion points for the work package leader to discuss with the rest of the work package.

In the following, a sample of the constructive evaluation of each work package will be presented:

WP1

Project characteristics:

Work package 1 scores 3.0 in pace, 2.0 in novelty, 2.0 in technology and 2.0 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 9.0, which is considered as a moderate score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP1

Project processes:

The work package scores 2.7 in flow, 3.3 in impact and 2.7 in leadership. This gives an average score of 3.0, which means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Figure: HDM score, WP1

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP1, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider getting WP leader ownership of the Impact Cases, that WP1 develops for the other WPs in order to ensure the Impact Cases are actually used – for instance via review workshops/meetings.
2. Consider if the Impact practice “impact solution design” can be used to frontload the project and create value sooner.
3. Consider when and how the intention of using the two Flow practices of “short and fat projects” and “rhythm in key events” is best realized.

WP2

Project characteristics:

Work package 2 scores 2.0 in pace, 2.0 in novelty 4.0 in technology and 2.4 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 10.42, which is considered as a moderate score. The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP2

Project processes:

The work package scores 2.7 in flow, 1.7 in impact and 3.0 in leadership. This gives an average score of 2.68, which means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Figure: HDM score, WP2

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP2, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider to create pulsechecks to get a systematic feedback from stakeholders within the WP on a monthly basis. Pulse checks create the insights and dialogue needed amongst key stakeholders.
2. Consider how and when the WP can have a fixed rhythm in key events, ex with sprints or status meetings every month.
3. Consider and discuss within the work package, how you can make the most of the Impact Case that has been developed.

WP3

Project characteristics:

Work package 3 scores 1.0 in pace, 1.0 in novelty, 1.0 in technology and 1.5 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 4.5, which is considered a low score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP3

Project processes:

Figure: HDM score, WP3

The work package scores 2.0 in flow, 1.7 in impact and 3.0 in leadership. This gives an average score of 2.6, which means that the work package is assessed not to use the Half double methodology yet (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP3, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider and discuss how you can increase the project leaderships across countries? Fixed meetings are already established, but how can you get the most out of it?
2. Consider to implement pulse checks when new employee starts, phd. and post doc.

WP4

Project characteristics:

Work package 4 scores 2.0 in pace, 3.0 in novelty, 3.0 in technology and 2.5 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score =10.5, which is considered as a moderate score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP4

Project processes:

Figure: HDM score, WP4

The work package scores 2.3 in flow, 2.7 in impact and 3.3 in leadership. This gives an average score of 2.95, which means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP4, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider and discuss whether some sub-projects could be involved to complement and enhance the findings of this work package?
2. Consider how to implement visual planning tools and what effect this might have on the overall workflow of the work package?

WP5

Project characteristics:

Work package 5 scores 1.0 in pace, 2.0 in novelty, 3.0 in technology and 2.3 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 8.25, which is considered as a moderate score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP5

Project processes:

The work package scores 4.0 in flow, 1.7 in impact and 3.3 in leadership. This gives an average score of 3.11, which means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Figure: HDM score, WP5

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP5, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider to create pulse checks to get a systematic feedback from stakeholders within the WP on a monthly basis. Pulse checks create the insights and dialogue needed amongst key stakeholders.
2. Consider and discuss within the work package, how you can make the most of the Impact Case that has been developed.

WP6+WP7

Project characteristics:

Work package 6+7 scores 2.0 in pace, 2.0 in novelty, 3.0 in technology and 2.8 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 9.83, which is considered as a moderate score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP6+7

Project processes:

Figure: HDM score, WP6+7

The work package scores 2.0 in flow, 3.0 in impact and 3.0 in leadership. This gives an average score of 2.53, which means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP6+7, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider and discuss within the work package, how you can make the most of the Impact Case that has been developed
2. Consider how to implement visual planning tools and what effect this might have on the overall workflow of the work package?

WP8

Project characteristics:

Work package 8 scores 2.0 in pace, 2.0 in novelty, 1.5 in technology and 2.0 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 7.46, which is considered as a moderate score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP8

Project processes:

The work package scores 2.0 in flow, 2.7 in impact and 2.7 in leadership. This gives an average score of 2.97, means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Figure: HDM score, WP8

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP8, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider how to create a fixed and stabile rhythm in the WP that can increase the flow.
2. Consider to do pulsechecks within the workpacks to be in touch with the pulse of the employee.
3. Consider if and how you can increase the use of technology within the WP.

WP9

Project characteristics:

Work package 9 scores 2.0 in pace, 1.0 in novelty, 1.0 in technology and 2.3 in complexity. Thus, the project scale score = 6.33, which is considered as a moderate score.

The characteristics of the work package are illustrated in the spiderweb chart.

Figure: Scale of WP9

Project processes:

The work package scores 2.3 in flow, 2.0 in impact and 3.0 in leadership. This gives an average score of 2.84, which means that the work package is assessed to use the Half double methodology (>2.5).

The project processes are illustrated in the figure.

Figure: HDM score, WP9

Questions for reflections:

Based on the conclusive evaluation of WP9, the following questions are proposed for consideration:

1. Consider to do pulse checks within the workpacks to be in touch with the pulse of the employee.
2. Consider how to create a fixed and stabile rhythm in the WP that can increase the flow.
3. Consider and discus within the work package, how you can make the most of the Impact Case that has been developed.

SUMMARY

Based on the first baseline interview with the FEMaLe project's 10 work packages, 9 work packages score to have a moderate project scale score. 1 work packages score to have a low project scale score.

All work packages, 10 out of 10, have in the first year of the project managed to implement the Half Double methodology into their daily work.